

D7.10: 3rd Pro-Enrich event annual report

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Executive summary

The Pro-Enrich event annual report is a compendium that documents different communication and dissemination activities conducted within the Pro-Enrich project.

This 3rd edition of the Pro-Enrich event annual report covers the period of M25 to M42 and includes consortium meetings, steering committee meetings and partner participation in relevant events, including six organised by the consortium, where Pro-Enrich dissemination activities have been conducted.

Different types of audiences have been targeted including the general public, the scientific community, industries and relevant networks. Both academic and industry Pro-Enrich partners have contributed significantly to dissemination activities.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Pro-Enrich event annual report is a compendium that documents different communication and dissemination activities conducted within the Pro-Enrich project. This 3rd edition covers the period M25 to M42 which is longer than the previous two reports due to the extension of the project caused by Covid-19. In the following sections, illustrative examples of activities are given for the final period of the project. The activities cover consortium meetings, steering committee meetings, as well as “dissemination activities and events”. For a complete list/overview of events, see the “Dissemination & communication plan” (D7.1 to D7.4).

2. CONSORTIUM MEETINGS

During the reporting period covered in this report (M25 to M42) five general assemblies have been conducted in the consortium.

- M25 meeting, May 12th - 13th, 2020, virtually via Teams
- M31 meeting, November 3rd -5th, 2020, virtually via Teams
- M37 meeting, May 10th – 12th, 2021, virtually via Teams
- M41 meeting, September 13th, 2021, virtually via Teams
- M42 meeting, October 13th – 15th, 2021, in Copenhagen and virtually via Teams

Picture 1: Screenshot from presentation at GA meeting May 12th, 2020

2.1. M25 meeting

The Pro-Enrich 5th general assembly was hosted by DTI over Teams (picture 1). This was the first meeting that took place after Covid-19 travel restrictions were introduced. It was intended to take place with GEA as hosts in Oelde, Germany, and despite them offering continuously to host, if possible, this never happened because of the pandemic. At the meeting the general progress

of the project work packages was discussed along with the delays caused by Covid-19 and how best to manage these.

2.2. M31 meeting

The Pro-Enrich 6th general assembly was once again hosted by DTI via Teams. In this meeting, among other things, DTI presented the work done with rapeseed and the results achieved and the partners commented and provided ideas for improving results in the coming trials. Natac presented their work on pilot-upscaling and Innorenew presented their work on glucosinolates. Finally, end users presented their results with testing of the samples for their respective applications.

2.3. M37 meeting

The Pro-Enrich 7th general assembly was also hosted by DTI via Teams. Apart from the general progress presentations and discussions, this was the meeting in which the second business model workshop took place. The purpose of this workshop was to discuss how to proceed with the results achieved so far and making sure that the partners involved had a say in this. The workshop was moderated by the exploitation manager. More information about this workshop is available in D7.12.

2.4. M41 meeting

A short preparatory meeting was held before the final event in October. The WP leaders gave an overview of the most important advances in their respective WPs and the consortium discussed which main messages the partners each wished to convey to the audience at the final event. To help in the discussion, the coordinator had prepared a number of questions using Mentimeter.

2.5. M42 meeting

The final general assembly meeting took place in Copenhagen in October of 2021 and was a hybrid meeting. It was attended physically by six project partners (NATAC, GEA, Tailorzyme, Emmelev, FBCD and DTI) and the remaining partners remained at home due to travel restrictions or concern about infection rates and attended virtually via Teams (picture 2). It was a three-day meeting where the second day consisted of the final event in the project as well as the fifth pre-market stimulation event.

The meeting concluded the various project activities and included an exploitation discussion which outlined the exit strategy, which is the basis of deliverables D.13 and D.14.

Picture 2: Group photo from hybrid general assembly in M42

3. STEERING COMMITTEE MEETINGS

The steering committee consists of the work package leaders and the coordinator. In this reporting period seven steering committee meetings have been conducted to keep track of project progress. Meetings in M28, M32 and M35 took place in between general assemblies with the meeting in M32 held specifically to discuss the way forward for Pro-Enrich after the exit of Vertech from the project:

- M25 steering committee meeting, May 13th, 2020, via Teams
- M28 steering committee meeting, August 25th, 2020, via Teams
- M31 steering committee meeting, November 5th, 2020, via Teams
- M32 steering committee meeting, December 11th, 2020, via Teams
- M35 steering committee meeting, March 12th, 2021, via Teams
- M37 steering committee meeting, May 12th, 2021, via Teams
- M40 steering committee meeting, August 20th, 2021, via Teams

In the picture 3 below is an example of meeting documentation for one of the meetings. More documentation is available in Annex I.

Picture 3: Minutes with screenshots from steering committee meeting August 20th, 2021

4. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES AND EVENTS

Dissemination activities are conducted within Work Package 7 (Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation), of which Food and Bio Cluster Denmark is work package leader. The 1st, 2nd, and 3rd Dissemination & communication plans (D7.1, D7.2, and D7.3) have described how to disseminate to the following target groups:

- All target groups (including the general public)
- Research and scientific community
- Industries
- Existing networks
- Political organizations

In the following section lists and examples of relevant activities are provided in relation to different target groups.

4.1. All target groups (including the general public)

In the past 1.5 year since the last event report in M24 Pro-Enrich partners have been quite restricted by Covid-19 as many events have been cancelled due to the infection risk involved when many people gather physically. Virtual events have been possible, but the general public is much less likely to attend virtual events than for example food fairs, science weeks, and similar open, physical events. However, consortium partners have participated in the following events where the target group has been relatively broad to present the Pro-Enrich project:

- Webinar about food waste at Madrid Science Week, October 10th, 2020.

- RTO Innovation Summit, November 18th, 2020, virtual event.
- The future of food - Unlocking the benefits of Scotland's circular economy, November 26th, 2020, virtual event.
- Pro-Enrich final event: From residue to revenue - Scaling up biosolutions, October 14th, 2021, Copenhagen & virtual.

One such event was the RTO Innovation summit which was a virtual event with 1000 participants from policy, research, and industry focusing on the European Green Deal, tackling the challenges of our time, and maintaining European leadership and technological and industrial competitiveness.

Anne Christine Hastrup, coordinator of Pro-Enrich, was one of the 50 speakers talking about the bio-based side of circular economy, exemplified in the Pro-Enrich project among others (Picture 4).

Picture 4: Screenshot from YouTube from RTO Innovation Summit aftermovie

Watch the whole event video [here](#), where Anne Christine appears several times both as a speaker and in a panel debate.

Another broad event was *The Future of Food – Unlocking the benefits of Scotland’s circular economy* - a virtual event organised by [Zero Waste Scotland](#) in which FBCD, represented by Louise Krogh Johnson, was invited on day two to give a presentation on behalf of the project on our efforts in transforming rapeseed cake into edible protein (Picture 6).

Picture 5: Front page of the event. Picture 6: Dissemination manager Louise Krogh Johnson, FBCD presenting the Pro-Enrich project

The purpose of the event was to illuminate various alternative ways of producing protein for human and animal consumption. Approx. 50 people attended the webinar, including Africa Pardavilla from project partner Innovarum.

Our own Pro-Enrich final event, *From residue to revenue – Scaling up biosolutions*, is also included in this category. It was an open event that took place in Copenhagen, but participants also had the option of virtual attendance. The programme included a presentation from Anne Christine Hastrup (DTI) about the Pro-Enrich project in general, one from Dominik Krienke (GEA) about processing of vegetable protein, and from NATAC’s Jose M. Pinilla about how NATAC identifies and selects side streams with technical and commercial potential for extraction of valuable bioactive components. Furthermore, we had organised a virtual keynote speech from Michael Nettersheim, Managing Partner in European Circular Bioeconomy Fund (ECBF), from his holiday home in Austria. He spoke about what parameters they evaluate biosolutions investment cases on. Finally, we gathered a panel consisting of entrepreneurs, companies, investors, and scientists – this included Nelo Emerencia representing BIC, Eric-Alan Rapp (The Danish Growth Fund), Katrine H. Ellegård (Consultant), Mathias Greve-Poulsen (KMC Ingredients), Ole Kaae Hansen (OK Biotech), Anne Christine Hastrup (DTI), Nelo Emerencia (BIC) and Michael Nettersheim (ECBF) (Picture 7). The panel debate which was moderated by exploitation manager Lars Horsholt Jensen (FBCD) had a very good discussion about the challenges we are facing as a planet and how investors can take responsibility for helping advance biosolutions in various industries by accepting risks. The event was attended by approx. 70 people – half physically present, and half attending virtually.

Picture 7: Panel debate. From the left Lars Horsholt Jensen (FBCD, moderator), Eric-Alan Rapp (The Danish Growth Fund), Katrine H. Ellegård (Consultant), Mathias Greve-Poulsen (KMC Ingredients), Ole Kaae Hansen (OK Biotech), Anne Christine Hastrup (DTI). On screen from the left: Nelo Emerencia (BIC) and Michael Nettersheim (ECBF)

4.2. Research and scientific community

Pro-Enrich partners have also participated in events targeted at the research and scientific community (some overlap with the broader activities as there was also a scientific focus). These include:

- Aarhus University iNANO autumn school, October 23rd, 2020, Aarhus, Denmark
- RTO Innovation Summit, November 18th, 2020, virtual event
- The future of food - Unlocking the benefits of Scotland's circular economy, November 26th, 2020, virtual event.
- Madrid Science Week, November 11th, 2020, Madrid, Spain, virtual event.
- Pro-Enrich featured as a case presented by Baudewijn Morgan, Head of H2020 unit, Welsh Government, in webinar "The Importance of the EU Regions in Welsh Innovation – A practical approach", March 2nd, 2021.
- EU Green Week 2021 online partner event: agri-food Innovative solutions towards #ZeroPollutionEU, May 31st, 2021, virtual event.

One example of a dissemination activity that targeted the research and scientific community was “The Importance of the EU Regions to Welsh Innovation – a Practical Approach” (Picture 8). This event attracted 86 live attendees from around Europe. It included presentations from the regions of East Netherlands, South Holland, the Basque Country and Baden-Württemberg on their interests in collaboration with Wales. Please click the link below to see the presentation that the Welsh Government gave in which Pro-Enrich is mentioned as a case (approx. 21 minutes in) thanks to Bangor University: <https://waterfront.eventscase.com/EN/innovation/on-demand>

Picture 8: Pro-Enrich slide from Welch Government presentation

Another example was the event “Agri-food Innovative solutions towards #ZeroPollutionEU” organised by project partner Innovarum. It was part of EU GreenWeek 2021 (Picture 9). This e-Workshop presented innovative projects in the agri-food sector— with speakers from active EU projects: GREENPROTEIN, PRO-ENRICH, BIOSCHAMP, BIOFRUITNET, COOPID, HOOP or VALUEWASTE—and their contributions to a zero-pollution transformation in the European Union. From the Pro-Enrich consortium Anne Christine Hastrup, Coordinator participated.

About 95 of the users connected during the event, with a maximum concurrency of 65 attendees. Most of the viewers came from countries within the EU (especially Spain and Germany). In total, there were attendees from 25 countries all around the globe.

The event was directed towards industry stakeholders and the business sector, with the aim of benefiting from the knowledge exchange and networking opportunity.

More information about the event, including the Pro-Enrich presentation given by DTI, can be found on [Innovarum’s website](#).

Picture 9: Official event image from Agri-Food innovative solutions towards a #ZeroPollutionEU

4.3. Industries

Pro-Enrich partners have participated in several events where the main audience was industry. The events include:

- EFIB 2020, October 10th, 2020, virtual event.
- New plant-based ingredients - New cooperation Protein Industries Canada, April 15th, 2020, virtual event.
- EUBCE 2021, April 28th, 2020, virtual event.
- Murcia Food 2021, May 17th, 2020, virtual event.
- Pro-Enrich pre-market stimulation events:
 - o Upcycling citrus and tomato biomass for high value applications, June 30th, 2021, virtual event.
 - o Processing of rapeseed meal and other raw materials for protein extraction, July 1st, 2021, virtual event.
 - o Replacing petrochemicals in adhesives – Our experience with rapeseed protein, July 6th, 2021, virtual event.
 - o Upcycling food waste into new proteins and functional ingredients, July 12th, 2021, virtual event.
 - o From residue to revenue – Scaling up biosolutions (afternoon programme), October 14th, 2021, physical/virtual event.

As this is the last part of the project period, in the above-mentioned events project partners shared non-confidential results from the Pro-Enrich project. For example, Innovarum gave a poster presentation at EFIB 2020 and created the poster below for the event (Picture 10).

Picture 10: EFIB 2020 poster created by Innovarum

Another example is that on April 15th, 2021, Food & Bio Cluster organised a Danish-Canadian event (not related to the Pro-Enrich project) where DTI was invited to give a presentation titled *Pilot scale transformation of biomass into feed/food products – enabling sustainable processing of novel and underutilized bioresources*. This presentation which was given by Dr. Anne Christine Hastrup included information about the Pro-Enrich project to the 34 Danish and Canadian attendees. Other speakers included Dr. James House, Professor, Department of Food and Human Nutritional Sciences, University of Manitoba, Faculty of Agricultural and Food Sciences and Gord Flaten, CEO, Avena Foods. The programme is available [here](#).

Pre-market stimulation

One of the important tasks in WP7 was to organise five pre-market stimulation events that were directed specifically towards industry stakeholders/end-users of the products developed in the project. The initial plan was to have these events as physical events at the industry partners' premises, but Covid-19 made this impossible. We then revised the plan and created four videos directed at the food, adhesives, processing, and cosmetics industries and premiered these at four different webinars with presentations and Q&A's from relevant project partners. The webinars were moderated by the dissemination manager Louise Krogh Johnson from FBCD. Please find below descriptions of each pre-market stimulation event:

Cosmetics industry: Upcycling citrus and tomato biomass for high value applications

On June 30th, 2021, Pro-Enrich partners Food & Bio Cluster Denmark and NATAC held a pre-market stimulation webinar directed towards the cosmetics, nutraceuticals and animal feed industries about the work done in the project on extraction of valuable components from citrus and tomato biomass. Louise Krogh Johnson from FBCD presented the project and Jose Maria Pinilla from NATAC gave the participants some interesting insights into the work they have done on extraction of lycopene from tomato biomass and hesperidin from citrus fruit. Jose explained what kind of valuable compounds these biomasses contain and what purposes they can serve in various products. He also touched upon some of the challenges involved, like stabilising the biomass before transport and use.

The cosmetics video is available here: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XwwhG_J9laI.

Processing industry: Processing of rapeseed meal and other raw materials for protein extraction

On July 1st, 2021, DTI, GEA, and Food & Bio Cluster Denmark spoke at the second Pro-Enrich pre-market stimulation webinar which put spotlight on processing technologies for protein extraction from rapeseed meal and other raw materials. Louise Krogh Johnson from Food & Bio Cluster Denmark presented the project. Dominik Krienke from GEA explained what skills and technology GEA possesses that can help utilise vegetable biomass for extraction of novel proteins and other functional ingredients as well as how they contributed to the Pro-Enrich project, and Anne Christine Hastrup introduced participants to the work done at DTI on processing rapeseed meal at their pilot plant.

The processing video is available here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Hu6QUcYkcmc>.

Adhesives industry: Replacing petrochemicals in adhesives – Our experience with rapeseed protein

On July 6th, 2021, CHIMAR, DTI, and Food & Bio Cluster Denmark held the Pro-Enrich project's third pre-market stimulation webinar specifically addressing the adhesives industry. The topic was the experience from the Pro-Enrich project on replacing petrochemicals with bio-refined rapeseed protein derived from the process residue from biodiesel production from project partner Emmelev. Louise Krogh Johnson gave a short introductory presentation of the project. Angelica Tamayo Tenorio from DTI told participants about the experiences with protein

extraction from rapeseed press cake and how lipid content presented one of the main challenges in connection to use in adhesives. Finally, Eleftheria Athanassiadou and Sophia Tsiantzi from CHIMAR introduced their company and its long history of innovation in the adhesives industry, and shared project results from the lab and performance tests of plywood panels with resin containing up to 40% rapeseed protein replacing conventional petrochemically derived phenols. The adhesives video is available here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1U0X8szTxL0>.

Food industry: Upcycling food waste into new proteins and functional ingredients

On July 12th, 2021, Tate & Lyle, DTI and Food & Bio Cluster Denmark held the fourth Pro-Enrich pre-market stimulation webinar addressing the food industry. William Ballantyne from Tate & Lyle explained, among other things, what they have done in the project in terms of application tests of the rapeseed protein produced at the pilot plant at DTI and what properties they are looking for in functional proteins. Marcel Tutor Ale from DTI, explained how he and his colleagues have processed the rapeseed processing residue at their pilot plant and went into some technical process details, and Louise Krogh Johnson gave a brief introduction to the project at the beginning.

The food video is available here: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a5yuTEX_8RE.

All industries: From residue to revenue – Scaling up biosolutions (afternoon programme)

On October 14th after the main event and a networking lunch the fifth pre-market stimulation event took place at the Danish Technological Institute in Copenhagen. At this event there were physical partner exhibition booths attended by project partners Emmelev, FBCD, DTI and GEA, where product samples were displayed, and people were ready to speak to the attendees. Innorenew, Tate & Lyle, Bangor University, and CHIMAR attended remotely by appearing via online Teams meetings on laptops at tables available for conversations with anyone interested either who was physically present in the room or who chose to join their Teams meeting (Picture 11).

Picture 11: The booths of Emmelev (left) and CHIMAR (right) at the fifth pre-market stimulation event on October 14th, 2021

The event also included guided tours to the DTI pilot plant in which many of the Pro-Enrich process trial activities have been carried out.

4.4. Existing networks

Pro-Enrich partners have been in contact with several relevant networks and organisations. The networks and organisations that have been contacted include:

- Chil.org
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)
- LIAISON
- Welsh Government
- North Wales Regional Engagement Team
- Partnership for sustainable biorefining (Partnerskab for Bæredygtig Bioraffinering)
- EUBioNet Network
- Biorefine Cluster Europe
- EIP-Agri

4.5. Political organizations

Pro-Enrich partners have been involved in three activities where the target audience has been politicians, political organizations or ministries.

On November 5th, 2020, Food & Bio Cluster Denmark had a visit from Morten Løkkegaard, Danish EU parliament member for the party Venstre, and Vice Chair of the Renew Europe Group among other things (Picture 12). FBCD gave a presentation about relevant activities, incl. Pro-Enrich, BBI and how EU can be a catalyst for innovation, cooperation and partnership.

Picture 12: Visit from Morten Løkkegaard (left) at Food & Bio Cluster Denmark (then Agro Business Park) office in Aarhus. Meeting attended by Pro-Enrich exploitation manager, Lars Horsholt Jensen (right) and former WP7 leader Kell Andersen (taking the picture).

Shortly thereafter, on November 10th, 2020, exploitation manager, Lars Horsholt Jensen, was invited to an interview about new trends and challenges facing the food & bioresource industry in Denmark by the director of business economy in the Danish Ministry of Industry, Business and Financial Affairs. This was for an analysis about future policy initiatives for clusters in Denmark.

Pro-Enrich was used as an example of sustainable, climate-friendly protein production reducing the carbon footprint of e.g. pet food.

Finally, both DTI and FBCD have been invited to participate in a national Danish working group focused on biosolutions which includes five ministries in Denmark (Picture 13):

- Ministry of Industry, Business and Financial Affairs
- Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries
- Ministry of Environment
- Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities
- Ministry of Higher Education and Science

DAGSORDEN

- 1. **Velkommen** v/Erhvervsministeriet
- 2. **Kort om samarbejdsprojektets baggrund, formål og arbejdsopgaver** v/Erhvervsministeriet
- 3. **Bordet rundt:** medlemmerne præsenterer sig selv og forventninger til samarbejdsprojektet
- 4. **Præsentation af analyser vedr. biosolutionssektorens potentialer** v/HBS Economics & Iris Group
- 5. **Præsentation af forhenværende samt eksisterende initiativer på biosolutionsområdet i nationalt- og EU-regi** v./ Ministeriet for Fødevarer, Landbrug og Fiskeri & Uddannelses- og forskningsministeriet
- 6. **Anbefalinger fra Væksteam Sjælland og øerne og rammeaftale om opfølgning på de regionale vækstteams' anbefalinger** v/ Jørn Stryger, formand for Væksteam Sjælland og øerne og Merete Woltmann, chefkonsulent i Erhvervsstyrelsen
- 7. **Plenum-drøftelse af foregående præsentationer**
- 8. **Erhvervsvenlig regulering** v/Erhvervsstyrelsen
- 9. **Forslag til emner, der skal drøftes på kommende møder**
- 10. **Evt.**

27. NOVEMBER 2021

Picture 13: Agenda for biosolutions meeting, incl. all ministry logos

A group of leading stakeholders from policy, research, industry, and were selected by the Danish Ministry of Industry, Business and Education to gather five times over the course of a year discuss how to address some of the barriers that different types of biosolutions companies/technologies face – for example regarding access to upscaling facilities, national and EU regulation, and consumer perceptions and lack of awareness or misunderstandings about new product type (Picture 14). At the first meeting on September 27th, 2021, FBCD informally informed the group about the results of the Pro-Enrich public perception study on alternative proteins and bio-based products carried out in WP6.

Food and Bio Cluster

ERHVERVSMINISTEREN

Kære Louise Krogh Johnson

Efter indstilling fra Food and Bio Cluster, har jeg besluttet at udpege dig som medlem af Samarbejdsprojekt om biosolutions fra d.d. Du er udpeget frem til, at Samarbejdsprojekt om biosolutions' funktionsperiode ophører den 31. november 2022.

Som det fremgår af vedlagte kommissorium, skal medlemmerne i samarbejdsprojektet drøfte, hvordan potentialet i biosolutions/bioøkonomi kan indfries. Det forventes, at samarbejdsprojektet kobler og samler viden på tværs af ministerier og erhvervsområdet samt fokuserer på hele værdikæden lige fra grundforskning over forskning og udvikling, pilot- og demonstrationsindsatser til kommercialisering.

Første møde i samarbejdsprojektet forventes afholdt den 27. september 2021 kl. 14.00-16.30 i Erhvervsministeriet. Du bedes bekræfte din deltagelse senest d. 24. september kl. 10.00.

Såfremt du har nogle spørgsmål, kan du rette henvendelse til fuldmægtig i Erhvervsministeriet, Mads Kjær Poulsen, på mail makjpo@em.dk og på tlf. 91 39 94 23.

Jeg ser frem til, at vi får skabt en konstruktiv dialog om potentialerne ved biosolutions.

Med venlig hilsen

Carsten Joensen
Kontorchef, life science
Erhvervsministeriet

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Picture 14: FBCD appointment letter from the Ministry of Industry, Business and Financial Affairs

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

During the project period from May 2020 to end of October 2021 (M25 to M42) the Pro-Enrich partnership has conducted and participated in a significant number of relevant events and dissemination activities. The activities and events include

- Five general assemblies (4 virtual, 1 physical)
- Seven steering committee meetings (all virtual)
- Dissemination activities targeting Pro-Enrich stakeholders (13 virtual, 3 physical)

Despite Covid-19 putting severe limitations on travels and events in the project period, we managed to still maintain close contact between project partners and reach various stakeholders with information about the project.

ANNEX 1 – Additional meeting documentation

General Assemblies

M31 November 4th, 2020

Pro-Enrich General Assembly & Steering Committee Meeting - Day 1

01:46:30 13 of 35 Take control

You're recording You are recording this meeting. Be sure to let everyone know that they are being recorded. Privacy policy Dismiss

Isothiocyanates

No detection of isothiocyanates in sample 3

Isothiocyanate	S1 - Oven dried, blended and sieved, Batch 9	S2 - Final Product, Batch 8	S4 - Spray dried, Batch 13	S5 - Spray dried, Batch 14
$C_6H_{13}NS_2$	✓		✓	✓
$C_{10}H_{19}NS_2$	✓			
$C_8H_{11}NS_2$		✓		

Sample	Material	Original ID
Sample 1	Oven dried, blended, sieved	Batch 9
Sample 2	"Final product"	Batch 8
Sample 3	Spray dried final product	Batch 11
Sample 4	Spray dried final product	Batch 13
Sample 5	Spray dried final product	Batch 14

Participants

- Natanya Majbritt Louie Hansen (Organizer)
- Adam Charlton (Outside your organization)
- Africa Pardavila (Guest)
- Alba Ramos (Natac) (Invitado) (Guest)
- Ana Miklavcic Visnjec (Guest)
- Anne Christine Steenkjer Haa...
- Chelson, Seronel (Outside your organization)
- ELEFTHERIA ATHANASIADOU (Outside your organization)
- Isabel Sambblas (Invitado) (Guest)
- Jose (Natac) (Invitado) (Guest)
- Kell Andersen - Food & Bio CL... (Outside your organization)
- Kelly Fleeters (Outside your organization)

M37 May 10th, 2021

Pro-Enrich: General Assembly Meeting Maj 2021 M37, Day 1

19:40 Request control

WP1

Partner updates

- Leitat has joined the consortium
 - New leader of WP6
 - Please welcome
 - Rubén Álvarez Hernández: Risk assessments, health and safety, and legislative study
 - David Wilde: Economic, environmental and social assessment tasks

Participants

- Eleftheria Athanasiadou (Outside your organization)
- Isabel Sambblas (Invitado) (Guest)
- jose - natac (Invitado) (Guest)
- Kiddi Elisa Brun Jensen (Outside your organization)
- Krienko, Dominik (Outside your organization)
- Louise Krogh Johnson - Food ... (Outside your organization)
- Maru (Outside your organization)
- Matthew Schwarzkopf (Outside your organization)
- Molltor, Maren (Outside your organization)
- Nicolas Juste Vidal (Outside your organization)
- Paul Baker (Outside your organization)

M41 September 13th, 2021

SC Meetings

M25 May 13th, 2020

M28 August 25th, 2020

M31 November 5th, 2020

M35 March 12th, 2021

M37 May 12th, 2021

M40 August 20th, 2021

The screenshot shows a Microsoft Teams meeting interface. The main content is a slide titled "WP4 Final test plan and pilot trials". The slide lists the following points:

- Upscaling of extraction step at GEA in Oelde:
 - Lab test to check acid precipitation of HPR protein (before summer), input for GEA trial
 - Extraction on the 13th-14th September in Oelde
 - Filtration steps at DTI the 15th-16th September
 - Emmelev has already sent raw material to GEA
 - Tairlozymes has sent enzymes for this trial
- Samples from previous batches sent to Tate&Lyle and Chimar, there was still enough material at DTI, which could be sent to end-users

The meeting interface includes a top bar with "Request control", a "Participants" sidebar on the right listing attendees like Alba Ramos (Natac), Angelica Tamayo Tenorio, and Anne Christine Steenkjaer Has..., and a bottom taskbar showing system information like "16°C Mest sol" and "20-08-2021".

Pro-Enrich: Development of novel functional proteins and bioactive ingredients from rapeseed, olive, tomato and citrus fruit side streams for applications in food, cosmetics, pet food and adhesives

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Project partners

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